

Kinship testing using X-STR linkage groups on a Tamil pedigree

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Abstract

X-chromosome Short Tandem Repeat (X-STR) markers are valuable supplements to autosomal STR testing in complex kinship cases, such as deficiency paternity and incest. The Investigator® Argus X-12 QS Kit enables multiplex typing of twelve X-STRs, clustered into four linkage groups, producing three-allele mini-haplotypes from male samples. This study evaluated the kit for kinship testing in a Tamil pedigree, involving eight males from three sets of full siblings who shared maternal grandparents, resulting in eight full sibling pairs and twenty first cousin pairs. Mothers' samples were included to confirm maternity and full sibling relationships. Buccal swabs were processed using Prep-n-Go™ Buffer and amplified with the Argus X-12 QS Kit. The VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit was used to successfully confirm all relationships. The X-STR results showed full male siblings shared one or two linkage groups. Among first cousins, five pairs shared no linkage groups, eight shared one, four shared two, and three shared three. The study demonstrates that first cousins with the same maternal grandparents can share more linkage groups than full siblings. Additionally, two rare events were observed: a recombination within a linkage group and a mutation. This study underscores the need for careful evaluation when using the Argus X-12 QS Kit for pedigree resolution involving first cousins, while recognizing the potential for rare events.

Keywords

Investigator® Argus X-12 QS Kit, X-STRs, linkage groups, kinship testing, recombination, mutation.

Introduction

Short Tandem Repeat (STR) markers located on the X chromosome (X-STRs) can supplement other genetic markers in kinship testing and complex forensic cases.

Their utility is particularly evident in deficiency paternity cases, where the putative father is unavailable for testing, and DNA profiles from sisters or stepsisters are sufficient to exclude paternity. X-STR testing is also valuable in incest cases, especially when the potential fathers are related, such as father and son. In these scenarios, the power of X-STRs can be considerably higher than that of autosomal markers [1-2]. This is due to the specific inheritance pattern of the X chromosome: females inherit one X chromosome from each parent, while males inherit only one from their mother. Recombination occurs only in females, meaning that sisters who share the same father inherit the same paternal X chromosome, while the maternally inherited X chromosome results from the recombination of their mother's two X chromosomes.

However, because of the limited length of the X chromosome, the number of genetic markers that are independently transmitted to offspring is restricted. Only four linkage groups have been identified in which recombination is not expected [1,3-4]. The Investigator® Argus X-12 QS Kit, developed by Qiagen, offers multiplex typing of twelve X-STRs clustered into these four linkage groups, producing mini-haplotypes of three alleles from male samples [5]. Research into the use and characteristics of X-STRs is essential to fully support their application in forensic cases. To promote the utilisation of X-STRs, the utility of the Argus X-12 QS Kit for kinship testing was evaluated in a Tamil pedigree.

Material studied, methods, techniques

Study samples

After obtaining informed consent, samples were collected from eight Malaysian Indian (Tamil) male individuals, grouped into three sets of full siblings (Figure 1). The siblings shared the same maternal grandparents, resulting in eight pairs of full siblings and twenty pairs of first cousins. Samples were also collected from their mothers.

Figure 1: Tamil family pedigree.

DNA extraction and STR typing

Buccal swabs were processed using Prep-n-Go™ Buffer (Applied Biosystems™) [6] and amplified with the Investigator® Argus X-12 QS Kit (Qiagen), following the manufacturer's recommendations. Capillary electrophoresis was performed on an ABI Prism® 3500xL Genetic Analyzer, and DNA profiles were generated using GeneMapper® ID-X v1.6 software.

Confirmation of relationships

Confirmatory relationship tests were conducted using the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit (Applied Biosystems™) [7], applying maternity and full sibling probability thresholds of 99.99% and 95%, respectively.

Results

Maternity and full sibling relationships were all confirmed. Typing of the mothers' profiles revealed two rare events: a recombination between DXS10148 and DXS10135 within linkage group 1, and a one-step repeat-loss mutation at DXS10134. As highlighted in Figure 2, each pair of full siblings shared a minimum of one and a maximum of two linkage groups. Conversely, while five pairs of first cousins shared no linkage groups, eight pairs shared one, four pairs shared two, and three pairs shared three linkage groups.

	A1	A2	A3	A4	B1	B2	C1	C2
A1		1	1	2	3	2	1	3
A2	1		2	2	1	0	1	1
A3	1	2		2	1	1	1	0
A4	2	2	2		2	0	0	1
B1	3	1	1	2		1	0	2
B2	2	0	1	0	1		2	3
C1	1	1	1	0	0	2		2
C2	3	1	0	1	2	3	2	

Figure 2: Number of shared linkage groups between the tested individuals.

Discussion

X-STRs have proven to be informative markers for determining complex relationships, providing stronger statistical support when used in combination with autosomal markers, compared to autosomal testing alone. For instance, in a paternity case involving the mother, daughter, and the mother of the putative father, the Likelihood Ratio (LR) calculated from autosomal markers increased by almost 5×10^8 when the Argus X-12 X-STRs were added. As a result, the probability of paternity increased from 93% to 99.99999%, significantly enhancing the power of the test [4]. Additionally, X-STR analysis has shown potential in distinguishing certain second-degree relationships, which autosomal markers are unable to do. In attempts to differentiate between grandparental, avuncular, and half-sibling relationships, satisfactory LRs were obtained from the analysis of Argus X-12 markers only in cases where genetic incompatibilities were present. In other cases, low LRs were observed. Based on these findings, caution is recommended when using Argus X-12 markers alone to resolve pedigrees [8].

The results of this study emphasise the need for careful evaluation when using X-STRs and linkage groups for kinship assessment. It was found that first cousins with the same maternal grandparents could share more linkage groups than full siblings. This underscores the fact that analysing X-STR linkage groups alone is not always reliable for inferring biological relationships and should be approached with caution.

Furthermore, two rare events were observed in this study: a mutation and a recombination within a linkage group. A deficiency paternity case involving two

sisters and their mother had previously been reported, in which three rare events occurred [9]. Genetic mapping of X-STR loci has highlighted the presence of non-negligible recombination both within and between linkage groups, emphasising the importance of considering recombination rates when using these markers [10]. Accurate estimation of mutation rates is crucial for reliable interpretation of genetic evidence, as it can determine whether hypotheses are accepted or rejected. However, more research is needed to increase the amount of available data for different populations. While some kinship issues may not require consideration of linkage, in others ignoring it could result in either over- or under-quantification of the genetic evidence. Therefore, further efforts should be made to address these challenges and improve practice [11].

This study was conducted using a Tamil pedigree from the Malaysian Indian minority. A recent study examined X-STR frequencies in Malaysian Malay and Malaysian Chinese individuals, highlighting the importance of evaluating population data for ethnic minorities and admixed populations. However, the Indian minority, which represents approximately 6.6% of the Malaysian population, was not included in that study [12].

To ensure continued progress and support for the use of Argus X-12 kit markers, it is essential to evaluate population data, including mutation and recombination rates, to guarantee fair representation of all ethnicities.

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of careful evaluation when using the Argus X-12 QS Kit for pedigree resolution. While X-STR testing is a valuable tool in various forensic scenarios, its application in kinship testing involving first cousins with the same maternal grandparents should account for the possibility that cousins, by chance, may share more linkage groups than full brothers. The resolution of relationship cases should also consider the potential co-occurrence of rare events, such as recombination between closely located markers within the same linkage group.

Further studies should continue to investigate the characteristics of X-STRs, including mutation and recombination rates, to support their use in routine forensic cases. Larger and more diverse populations should also be explored to enhance databases, ensuring that data is available for a wide range of case scenarios. This will help ensure best practices and maximise the accuracy of results.

Conflict of interest statement

All claims made in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of their affiliated company or organisation.

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